

OR-to-ICU Handoff Following Cardiac Surgery

Vincent Risler, DNP, RN, Karanbir Sumra, DNP, RN, and Graham Valley, DNP, RN
Sassoon Elisha, EdD, CRNA, FAAN and Hannah Fraley, PhD, RN, CNE, CPH

Background

- Handoff is a process that involves the transfer of responsibility and care of a patient from one team of healthcare providers to another
- Handoff is a critical period in which pertinent safety information is relayed and an inadequate handoff can result in patient harm and adverse patient outcomes
- A standardized handoff tool may help to decrease the omission of patient information and thus increase patient safety

Problem & Purpose

Problem

Utilizing the PICO format, the problem identified was the lack of a structured, standardized handoff process when transferring patients from the cardiac OR to the ICU, which led to an omission of patient data

Purpose

To implement a standardized handoff tool to limit the omission of pertinent data with the hopes of decreasing adverse events to patients

Methods

- Review of literature and creation of handoff tool
- Pre-implementation audits
 - Variables of interest
 - Limits bias
- Staff focus groups
 - Identify themes
 - Ensures long-term compliance

Objectives and Aims

Objective

- Improve communication and decrease the omission of vital patient information during cardiac OR-to-ICU handoff

Aim

- To improve patient safety, with a cardiac surgery specific handoff tool focused on this high acuity patient population

Revised Iowa Model Conceptual Framework

Handoff Tool

OR to Cardiac ICU Handoff Report Sheet																	
Patient	(patient label)																
Allergies																	
Procedure																	
PMH																	
Anesthesia Type																	
Complications																	
Pre-Op Medications																	
AxC / CPB Time	/																
TEE Findings																	
Cardiac Rhythm	A / V																
Pacing Wires	Rate: _____																
Pacer Settings	Output: A: mA V: mA Sensitivity: A: mV V: mV																
Hemodynamic Goals																	
Misc.																	
Recent Labs	Time: _____ <table border="1"> <tr><td>Na</td><td>Cl</td><td>BUN</td><td>Cr</td></tr> <tr><td>K</td><td>CO2</td><td>Chol</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>PT</td><td>PTT</td><td>TG</td><td>LDL</td></tr> <tr><td>Hgb</td><td>Hct</td><td>WBC</td><td>PLT</td></tr> </table> Other: _____	Na	Cl	BUN	Cr	K	CO2	Chol		PT	PTT	TG	LDL	Hgb	Hct	WBC	PLT
Na	Cl	BUN	Cr														
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PT	PTT	TG	LDL														
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Current Infusions	<table border="1"> <tr><td>DOBUtamine</td><td>mcg/kg/min</td></tr> <tr><td>DOPamine</td><td>mcg/kg/min</td></tr> <tr><td>EPInephrine</td><td>mcg/min</td></tr> <tr><td>NORepinephrine</td><td>mcg/min</td></tr> <tr><td>Vasopressin</td><td>units/min</td></tr> <tr><td>Nitroglycerin</td><td>mcg/min</td></tr> <tr><td>Insulin</td><td>units/hr</td></tr> <tr><td>Propofol</td><td>mcg/kg/min</td></tr> </table>	DOBUtamine	mcg/kg/min	DOPamine	mcg/kg/min	EPInephrine	mcg/min	NORepinephrine	mcg/min	Vasopressin	units/min	Nitroglycerin	mcg/min	Insulin	units/hr	Propofol	mcg/kg/min
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Intake and Output	<table border="1"> <tr><td>IV Fluid</td><td>Crystalloid:</td></tr> <tr><td></td><td>Colloid:</td></tr> <tr><td>Blood Products</td><td>PRBC:</td></tr> <tr><td></td><td>PLT:</td></tr> <tr><td></td><td>FFP:</td></tr> <tr><td></td><td>CRYO:</td></tr> <tr><td></td><td>Cell Saver:</td></tr> </table>	IV Fluid	Crystalloid:		Colloid:	Blood Products	PRBC:		PLT:		FFP:		CRYO:		Cell Saver:		
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Sample & Setting

Sample

- Nurses currently working in the Cardiac ICU, anesthesia providers, and pertinent surgical staff involved in cardiac surgical cases

Setting

- Hospital based in Southern California which performs cardiac surgery

Discussion

- Implementation strategies should include focus groups of key stakeholders to identify necessary components not identified in the literature and incorporate staff feedback into the tool before roll out
- Evaluation may include biweekly audits over a two month span in order to compile data
- Data analysis may be conducted and the handoff tool may be improved utilizing the revised Iowa Model

Implications

- Given that the handoff tool is proven effective in achieving objectives, it may be implemented in other facilities in the future in order to maximize the impact of the tool